

FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE STUDENTS ON FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract. *The article shows the place of social competence in the system of key competencies in the application of the competence approach in education, and also defines the means, conditions and techniques for the formation of social competence in foreign language lessons.*

Keywords: *competence approach, key competencies, social competence, communicative competence, forms of education.*

A distinctive feature of the current stage of development of society is the rapidly unfolding innovative transformations of various spheres of human activity, including social. Society and the state today require a person to be able to socialize in a rapidly changing society, to possess universal methods of action. This is one of the reasons why, regardless of the classifications of key competencies, most scientists pay a significant place to social competence as readiness and ability to social interaction in different spheres of life, as a unity of social adaptation and mobility. Innovations in the education of our country point the way to school to find ways and means of developing the ability of an individual to adapt and ensure its social competence.

Social competence – social skills or responsibilities that allow a person to adequately fulfill social norms and rules. Researchers have found that social competence, firstly, reflects the interaction of a person and society; secondly, implies the possession of a person by means of interpersonal interaction; thirdly, it includes several components; fourth, it implies taking into account the correlation of one's own goals and the needs of the whole society.

Structure and content of social competence (according to A.V. Khutorsky) [8]:

Components

Content of components:

ability to be responsible for decision-making, take part in common decisions, set goals, result planning, analysis and reflection;

ability to control their activities; attention to problems related to achieving goals; ability to make decisions. The ability to hear, understand and take into account the needs of other people with whom you enter into communication. The ability to control your emotions. Intellectual focus on understanding another person;

emotional responsiveness, the ability to empathize; intuitive foresight of people's behavior. Social mobility, human activity. Willingness to work on non-standard and controversial issues; research of the environment to identify its capabilities and resources, willingness to use new and non-standard ideas to achieve the goal; setting for common success; personal responsibility for a joint cause.

Social competence does not exist outside of a particular society. It depends on the main characteristics of the life of a given society: economic and political life, historical and cultural norms, the organization of public relations. Social competence is not only a certain socialization a person, but also the ability to achieve success using social resources.

Psychologists divide social competence into a number of the following individual abilities:

- communicative competence,
- social entrepreneurship,
- general legal and economic literacy,
- the ability to understand the hidden, shadow features of society,
- the ability to lead (social confidence),
- the ability to understand social roles and interpersonal relationships,
- the ability to establish long-term partnerships,
- the ability to manage their own image.

Since the main purpose of teaching a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence, the ability to use language as a means of intercultural and interpersonal communication, the academic discipline "foreign language" is the subject of the school curriculum, which makes a major and significant contribution to the formation of students' social competence.

Success in intercultural communication is not possible without the formed social competence of students, that is, the formed opportunity to interact with others and feelings self-confidence, as well as the ability to take on various social roles and the ability to cope with current situations.

In our opinion, it is social competence, as a structural component of foreign language communicative competence, that should be given special attention due to the fact that it is this ability that serves language acquisition in the context of intercultural and interpersonal communication. It is necessary to make every effort to develop social competence, since there is a problem of participation in the dialogue, knowledge or ignorance of the peculiarities of communication with certain social groups, the language of which is being studied to ensure tolerance and security of communication for both sides. It is important to instill in students an interest in studying and understanding the culture of the countries of the language being studied, an interest in finding a common language and finding a compromise in difficult situations, because this enriches the personality of students with social and cultural knowledge, and also helps to use the accumulated communication skills in the future. The inclusion of a social component in the teaching of a foreign language by students in higher education serves to form a holistic picture of the world for students through expanding the scope of students' knowledge in various activities, familiarizing them with their cultural heritage, educating a patriot of their country and a citizen of the world who respects the views and opinions of the interlocutor, capable of free interpersonal and intercultural communication.

Awareness of the specifics of society, the development of a sense of tolerance for other views, broadens the horizons of students, increases the level of their general culture and motivation to learn foreign languages.

By including the use of elements of collective activity in the educational process and to intensify the educational process, using the latest teaching methods and techniques, improving educational skills and skills of independent work, group forms of cooperation, the teacher will be able to make the content of teaching students a foreign language more effective, focused on the personal attitudes of the student.

Modern state standard of basic general education sets tasks to achieve qualitatively new goals in learning a foreign language, namely: the development of foreign language communicative competence and all its components, where a special place is occupied by social competence, the

formation and development of which allows students to introduce a new social experience using a foreign language.

Thus, to form social competence means to teach students to interact with each other in the educational process when performing various communicative tasks.

Today, in the practice of teaching a foreign language, individual, frontal and group forms of organization of the educational process are distinguished. The individual form of organization of students' work means that a student independently performs the same tasks for the whole class without contact with other students, but at the same pace for everyone. The individual form of work is used at all stages of the lesson to solve various didactic tasks: the assimilation of new knowledge and their consolidation, the formation and consolidation of skills and abilities, for repetition and generalization of the material passed. It is most characteristic when performing independent and control tasks. However, for the formation of social competence, this form has a significant disadvantage – the student is isolated from other students while working on the task and only he is responsible for the success of this exercise.

With this form of organization of educational activities, students do not come into contact with other students, which prevents them from learning to be in society, solve disputes and problems, be part of a team. The frontal form of the educational organization student activity is a type of activity in the classroom in which all students of the group, under the direct guidance of the teacher, perform a common task. The work is carried out with the whole class at the same pace. In the process of telling, explaining, showing, the teacher strives to simultaneously influence all those present. The frontal form of the organization of educational activities of students in the classroom helps to establish close ones the relationship between the teacher and the class, the joint friendly work of students, during which common participation is achieved in solving not only educational, but also educational tasks, mutual assistance, the formation of stable cognitive interests, allows using a variety of methods and techniques to activate the learning process. More often it is used at the stage of primary assimilation of new material, with problematic, informational and explanatory-illustrative presentation, this form allows you to attract a maximum of students to active educational and cognitive activity.

Methodologists consider group learning activities of students to be one of the successful ways of forming social competence. And this is not accidental, because "educational activity is collective in nature and is a system of socially organized interactions, relationships and communication" [6]. Psychologists have proved that joint activity in the collective of students and teachers themselves is the initial form of individual activity and determines their mastery of such actions as goal-setting, planning, control and evaluation, without which learning is impossible.

To concretize learning activities, let's turn to the structure of group learning activities, which consists of the following links:

1. The motivational-orientation link assumes that students jointly analyze the conditions and their capabilities, as well as accept or set themselves a single educational task.

2. Executive link – updating of existing knowledge when performing a number of educational activities and tasks collectively or individually. Mutual support and exactingness to each other, the ability of adequate self-criticism, a sense of responsibility for the result of a common cause are especially necessary here.

3. Control and evaluation link – mutual control over the implementation of the actions of the previous stage and evaluation of the results of joint work.

Group work is used, as a rule, when performing speech exercises and tasks for the joint search for information and the collective solution of the problem situation.

Pair work, as one of the types of group work, is mainly used to perform exercises of various types: language and conditional speech. In practice, pair work is widely used to train language material, when students are offered cards with exercises for substitution, filling in gaps, transformation, etc. The organization of pair work to perform truly communicative exercises is often unmanageable, which is often the cause of negative results.

Pair and group work create favorable conditions for the formation of foreign language communication skills. In foreign language lessons, it is necessary to be able to organize specially, namely, to find an effective form of interaction between participants and to choose adequate means of managing them from the teacher's side. The content of joint educational activities has an impact on the skills and abilities included in the social competence.

Taking into account the specifics of the academic discipline "foreign language", it is possible to distinguish the components of the content of collective educational activity:

1. Knowledge of the language material, the peculiarities of its functioning, as well as the skills of its use in communication situations.

2. Methods of acquiring language knowledge, speech skills, as well as self- and mutual control techniques.

3. Mastery of the techniques of cooperation (joint solution of speech tasks for imitation, substitution and reproduction).

Based on the above, it is necessary to highlight such skills and abilities included in social competence as the ability to work together to achieve a common goal, support each other, the ability to adequately self-criticism, evaluate your personal contribution to the success or failure of a common cause, jointly analyze the conditions of the situation and correlate them with opportunities. Thus, in foreign language lessons, in order to form students' social competence, namely the ability to live in society, it is necessary to use such forms of educational organization that could simulate a real communication situation, give students the opportunity to interact with each other, listen, defend their point of view, correct their behavior and subordinate their interests to the interests of society as it happens in real life.

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